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**Advertising and PR Communications as a component of the curriculum for
bachelor's degree students majoring in Information, Library and Archival
Studies***

Advertising and PR Communications are important components of all branches of people's activities in the modern world. In this context, such discipline should be mandatory in the curriculum for bachelor's degree students majoring in Information, Library and Archival Studies as they are trained for the information work. The information work provides mastering skills in using advertising and PR Communications in realizing companies' goals as to managing people's demands and supply.

According to the curriculum for bachelor's degree students majoring in Information, Library and Archival Studies there is a mandatory course "Theory and Practice of Advertising and PR Communications" geared toward forming competencies concerning developing advertising and PR communications in the 5th semester. But the general concept about separate elements of advertising and PR communications students get within other mandatory disciplines during their learning: Theory and Practice of Documentation Science (1st semester), The Basis of Service and Communication in a Professional Area (1st semester), The Basis of Economics, Marketing and Management (2nd semester), Culturology (2nd semester), Information Culture of Professional Communication (3rd semester), the Basis of Esthetics and Industrial Design (4th semester), Multimedia technologies in the Information Activity (5th semester), Digital branched Journalism (7th semester), Presentations in the Science and Technical Branch (8th semester), etc. Separate aspects of advertising and PR communications students can also get by choosing elective courses such as Communications Skills Training, etc.

The course "Theory and Practice of Advertising and PR Communications" is designed to form a system of theoretical knowledge and applied skills for students to develop their advertising and PR communications to ensure effective communication in the academic and professional environment and achieve successful careers.

There are some objectives of the course including the study of the following:

- social impact of advertising and PR campaigns;
- advertising and PR technologies (campaign planning and research, copywriting, website design, etc.);
- creating and evaluating advertising and PR messages (advertising copywriting, etc.).

Among the expected learning outcomes are the following: to form strategies for system organization, modernization, and improving the management effectiveness of professional activities in Information, Library and Archival Studies.

The content of the course consists of two modules. Each of them consists of four themes.

The first module is devoted to theoretical and practical aspects of advertising communications and includes the following issues:

- considering the scientific apparatus of the discipline, the basic concepts of the course, its place among other sciences, and its significance for academic and professional activities. The theme of practical training within the theme is devoted to conceptual guidelines of the discipline for academic and professional activities;

- advertising impact on society, its theories, definitions, etc;
- requirements to modern advertising;
- advertising technologies for creating information products.

Within the 1st module, students can create original advertising, slogans, copywriting, and presentations by means of using modern software (Canva, Prezi, Visme, etc.).

In the 2nd theme, students can know everything about the theory and practice of PR communications including the following:

- understanding and challenges of PR communications;
- the essence of PR media and its classification
- types of PR services;
- applied aspects of using PR communications.

After studying the course, students must acquire knowledge and skills in different aspects of advertising and public relations including the essence of advertising, creative advertising techniques, principles of public relations, etc.

Students can realise practical skills they get in the course in the academic and professional environment during their practical classes and industrial practice before defending their qualification works.

Among important competencies they can get after the course students can get the following ones:

– General competence 6. Skills in the use of information and communication technologies for the implementation of professional communications for the provision of information products and services;

– Professional Competence 9. The ability to use PR and other applied social and communication technologies in the conditions of the modern information and technological infrastructure of institutions and enterprises of the information and service industry.

Besides them, students also get learning outcomes including the following ones:

– Learning Outcomes 2. Implement and use communication technologies in social systems, multimedia support of information activities, web design and web marketing technologies;

– Learning outcomes 9. Assess the possibilities of using the latest information, computer and communication technologies to improve practices in the production of information products and services.

The mandatory course “Theory and Practice of Advertising and PR Communications” allows bachelor’s degree students majoring in Information, Library and Archival Studies to master not only soft skills, which are in employers’ demands but also to realize their potential in professional careers for Ukraine’s prosperity.